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Recurrent Convolutional Neural Network based defect detection in Submerged Arc Welding processes

Estefania A. Tapia Suarez*, Inés Pérez Couñago, Christian Eike Precker, Juan
Manuel Fernández Montenegro and Santiago Muiños-Landín

AIMEN Technology Centre, Porriño 36410, Spain

* Corresponding author. Tel.: +34-986344000;. E-mail: estefania.suarez@aimen.es

Abstract. Detecting defects predictively during the welding process, such as porosity, is of vital importance as it allows for the avoidance of degradation in the quality, durability, and productivity of the weld. Research into predictively identifying these types of defects in Submerged Arc Welding (SAW) is quite limited due to the difficulty of gathering data along the process. This remains a challenge to drive the optimization of the manufacturing of pieces that include such welds as the case of large components like pipes in the oil and gas industry. Therefore, this work addresses this challenge and proposes a methodology based on a deep hybrid neural network called recurrent convolutional neural network (RCNN). This deep learning model is capable of detecting and predicting surface porosity defects in real-time using the continuous voltage electrical signal from the SAW process. The training of the RCNN model involved using various weld beads, some with surface porosity and others without. On the one hand, defects were labeled based on the location of the pores along the weld, while on the other hand, the voltage electrical signals were processed and organized. The proposed framework based on RCNN was tested in other weld beads, where the results were satisfactory with the model achieving a high accuracy rate of around 80% in predictive pore detection. Moreover, the model's processing time was < 10 ms, meeting the requirements for real-time applications.

Keywords: Submerged arc welding; Porosity; Weld quality; Predictive detection; Deep learning.

1 Introduction

Submerged Arc Welding (SAW) is a fusion welding process widely utilized across various sectors, including oil and gas, aeronautics, shipbuilding, and automotive industries.

Due to its extensive applications, the quality standards for components manufactured via this process are becoming increasingly stringent. Nonetheless, the emergence of defects, notably porosity, poses a significant challenge in SAW. Such defects result in substantial strength deterioration and alterations in the mechanical properties of the weld, consequently diminishing the durability and productivity of manufactured parts [1]. While ultrasonic inspection and radiographic inspection have traditionally served as nondestructive testing methods for defect detection, their utility is constrained by limitations in real-time detection, high costs, and applicability in large-scale production lines [2].

Different research studies have addressed this issue by developing online monitoring systems that utilize information from the welding process, including voltage, current, temperature, acoustic signals, images, etc.; information closely linked to weld quality [3,4]. However, in the case of SAW, the use of process parameters for developing online monitoring and defect detection algorithms has been limited, primarily due to challenges related to data collection and handling, as well as the complexity of the process. Relevant developments have been observed only in [5] and [6]. In these studies, learning models were implemented using images to detect online defects and monitor bead geometry, respectively. However, utilizing images requires special sensors to capture them due to the obscured view of the weld pool and the presence of flux. Other sensors, such as those for capturing electrical signals, offer greater advantages. These devices simplify real-time signal acquisition and are less susceptible to interference from the complex welding environment, providing greater stability. Specifically, the voltage signal has shown a strong correlation with the physics of the welding process [7]. Consequently, many studies in other processes such as GMAW or TIG have utilized this signal for online defect detection [8–10].

Deep learning (DL) techniques are currently a field of exponential evolution under scientific research and industry. Researchers have deployed DL techniques in online quality inspection to detect potential defects in various welding processes [11]. Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are among the most representative deep learning algorithms and are widely used in both image-based [5,12,13] and sequential signal-based defect classification [14]. However, the CNN model does not consider the temporal connection of the collected signals. Long short-term memory (LSTM), a subset of recurrent neural networks (RNN), is recognized for its prowess in time series analysis and intricate temporal pattern extraction [15]. The LSTM model is characterized by its adaptability and ability to address sequential data, making it particularly suitable for the analysis of electrical measurements of welding processes. The hybrid recurrent convolutional neural network (RCNN) model combines the strengths of both CNN and LSTM, where 1D-CNN extracts relevant special features from the input data and the LSTM layers capture temporal dependencies. RCNN has been successfully applied in various domains such as manufacturing related to welding defects automatic detection [16].

In this context, this work proposes a methodology for the real-time detection of porosity-related defects in SAW process. This methodology utilizes voltage signals in conjunction with the implementation of the deep hybrid neural network RCNN. The RCNN model offers several advantages, including automatic capturing of spatial and

temporal features of the data, as well as high potential for applicability and performance. Consequently, the proposed methodology is capable of predicting porosity occurrences based on the real-time progress of the weld. This serves as the foundation for the development of an adaptive control strategy, ultimately leading to the advancement of intelligent welding techniques.

2 Experimental System

The schematic diagram representing the SAW experimental system is depicted in Fig. 1. This diagram comprises the welding machine (Miller Summit Arc 1250), the control module, and the measurement sensors. The sensors utilized in this study, as shown in the diagram, are electrical sensors consisting of differential voltage and current probes. Specifically, the differential probes were installed between the welding machine and the welding plate. Synchronized voltage and current signals are recorded using an oscilloscope (PicoScope 2000) at a sampling rate of 2500 samples per second. The data is swiftly transferred to a computer for analysis and/or application development via a high-speed USB connection.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of SAW experimental system.

Several experiments were conducted on steel plates of various lengths, using the filler material 3.2 mm OE-SD3 and OP121TT flux. Additionally, different welding parameter settings were employed, as summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Normal welding settings parameters of SAW

Voltage	Current	Wire Feed Speed	Travel Speed
27 – 30 V	450 – 675 A	1.6 – 2.7 m/min	48 - 80 cm/min

To induce pore occurrence artificially, welding was performed in some experiments with plates and flux under humid conditions. Authorized personnel visually inspected the surface beads for defects along their entire length and recorded pores of various

sizes, ranging from 1 to 2.4 mm in diameter, that had formed along each bead. Similarly, experiments were conducted under ideal conditions where no defects occurred. This was done to evaluate the RCNN model's capability to detect pores in beads with and without porosity.

3 RCNN-based porosity detection

3.1 Model Overview

The hybrid deep learning RCNN model, composed of the CNN and LSTM models, can establish a relationship between voltage measurements of the SAW process and the porosity state. In this way, when the model is applied in real time during the welding process, there will be predictive information on the presence or absence of pores, which represents the basis for implementing control actions. Fig. 2 shows the overall framework of the RCNN model.

Fig. 2. Overall framework of RCNN model.

As shown in Fig. 2, voltage measurements obtained during the welding process are organized into sequential data and input into the RCNN model. The 1D-CNN layer is responsible for detecting local features and capturing short-term relationships from the electrical signal, such as trends or fluctuations that may not be seen at a glance. This enables the LSTM layer to be more efficient in capturing long-term temporal dependencies throughout the electrical signal sequence, thereby strengthening the anomaly detection capacity. This means CNN and LSTM complement each other in applications like this work, which focuses on porosity detection. Then, the fully connected layers establish relationships among the captured features, and the classifier provides the final determination, indicating the presence or absence of porosity defects.

3.2 RCNN Training

The input data for training the RCNN model consists of voltage measurements obtained from various weld beads and corresponding porosity state labels. Voltage

measurements undergo a process known as window sliding, wherein the data is partitioned into time series with a specified window length (measured in millimeters of welding). Conversely, porosity state labeling is conducted based on the visual inspection record of the weld beads.

Fig. 3(a) displays the voltage signal obtained during welding, a bead with various pores. Fig. 3(b) represents the porosity state labeling of this bead for each weld millimeter, where '0' indicates the pores' absence and '1' indicates the pores' presence. Finally, Fig. 3(c) illustrates the RCNN input data, comprising a voltage time series of a 4 mm length (depicted by the green shadow), along with the corresponding porosity labeling in the subsequent millimeter (depicted by the orange shadow). Consequently, each time series is trained to predict the porosity state in the following weld millimeter.

Fig. 3. Input data for RCNN training. (a) Voltage measurement; (b) Porosity state labeling; (c) window sliding into voltage time series along with porosity labels.

RCNN training involves establishing its architecture along with selecting hyperparameters that minimize the disparity between the model predictions and the true classification states. The established architecture of the RCNN is depicted in Fig. 4.

The convolutional layer includes specifications such as the number and size of convolutional kernels, while the LSTM layer comprises the number of memory units. Additionally, the classifier is composed of fully connected layers and corresponding activation functions, which determine the class with the highest probability.

Fig. 4. Representation of the RCNN architecture for porosity state classification.

It is worth mentioning that the loss function used is Weighted Cross-Entropy (WCE) [17]. This function has the advantage of addressing the class imbalance present in this classification task, where the minority class—porosity presence—is of greater interest. By incorporating a weight factor α , WCE allows for establishing a balance between the

two classes. Finally, in addition to the training model, an early stopping criterion was employed to avoid overfitting. This criterion involved monitoring the loss of the model on the test data. If the loss did not improve over 10 consecutive epochs, the training process was stopped. The model weights were then restored to the epoch where the best metric was achieved until the end of the training.

4 Results and Discussions

The RCNN deep learning model was developed in Python version 3.10.12 using TensorFlow 2.15.0 on a computer with an Intel Core i7-13800H @ 2.5 GHz processor and 32 GB of RAM. The training process was accelerated by utilizing a GPU machine, which allowed for linear scaling of the mini-batch size and faster computations.

The training was performed using data from 6 surface beads with porosity along their length. The six beads, ranging in length from 300 to 500 mm, make up a total length of 2050 mm. The time series window length was adjusted based on two premises: a) the model achieves great performance in the classification task, and b) the time required by the model to predict the porosity state is as short as possible, allowing sufficient time to implement some control action. In this context, RCNN training was performed with different window sizes of 1 mm, 2 mm, 3 mm, 4 mm, and 5 mm. The final window size will be the one that best meets the two mentioned premises.

Additionally, the database needed to undergo a normalization process due to the different voltage ranges handled in the welding beads. This process was carried out using the z-score algorithm [18]. Once the database was prepared in terms of its partitioning, window size, and normalization, RCNN training was conducted using the architecture mentioned in Section 3.2. The classification performance on the test dataset, as well as the RCNN execution time, is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. RCNN performance and time execution results (test data)

Window size	Precision	Recall	Time execution
1 mm	66,7 %	71,6 %	6,2 ms
2 mm	69,3 %	76,4 %	6,7 ms
3 mm	71,2 %	76,6 %	10,8 ms
4 mm	71,5 %	78,3 %	10,9 ms
5 mm	78,8 %	80,9 %	14,2 ms

From Table 2, the ability of RCNN to detect pores improves as the input window size increases. The best performance is achieved with an input window of 5 mm, where precision and recall are around 80%. However, as the input window increases, the time required by RCNN to detect the porosity state (PS) also increases. Given the real-time application requirements of this development, the PS detection time must be very fast (before porosity develops). Considering the fastest welding speed of Table 1 (80 cm/min), the time required to weld 1 mm is 75 ms, which implies that the detection time for PS should be less than 7.5 ms (10% of the time to weld 1 mm) to meet real-

time application requirements. From Table 2, it is observed that with a window size of 2 mm, the PS detection time is 6.7 ms, meeting the real-time application requirements, however, the model's performance is reduced to around 70% with this window size.

Given that in a real scenario, pores along the weld are the minority meaning that when one occurs, the RCNN model must be able to identify it, this work prioritizes the recall metric since it reflects the model's ability to identify minority instances (pores). Therefore, with a window size of 2 mm, where the PS detection time is only 6.7 ms, although the precision declines, the recall remains at a competitive value of 76.4%. Thus, this window size is selected for real-time applications.

In this case, the database size is 2420, which was generated based on a window size of 2 mm, a window slide of 1 mm, a sampling frequency of 2500 Hz, and a welding travel speed in the range of 48 to 80 cm/min. The data were partitioned into training (80%) and testing (20%), with the test data corresponding to different chunks of weld beads. Fig. 5 shows the confusion matrix of the model on the test data, and Fig. 6 exhibits the model's behavior on a chunk of weld, where a binary indicator represents the detection.

Fig. 5. Confusion matrix results on the test data.

Fig. 6. Porosity detection of RCNN model on a test weld chunk.

The confusion matrix in Fig. 5 shows the model's classification results on the test data. As can be seen, the model performs adequately in porosity detection, with a low presence of false positives (incorrect detection of porosity where it is not present) and false negatives (incorrect detection of porosity where it is present). Although these values are low, they could be improved. For example, increasing the database, especially with more instances containing pores, could provide a better balance between the classes, reduce the number of false positives and false negatives, and thus improve RCNN's performance.

The welding chunk shown in Fig. 6 has two pores in its final part, each with a diameter of 2 mm, which have been highlighted in red. Although a greater number of pores appear to be present throughout the welding, these are actually surface-coating oxidations that do not form cavities or holes like pores do. As shown in Fig. 6 through the binary indicator, the existing pores are detected, with only one false positive in this weld small chunk. Therefore, effective detection of pores, even of different sizes, is achieved through the application of the RCNN model, demonstrating its potential to meet real-time predictive requirements. Improving the classification results of the RCNN could also be achieved by adding another input variable to the model that is

related to the defect under study. For example, the variable related to welding plate temperature would be a suitable candidate, as it reflects the plate's heating state and the possibility of trapped gases, which can lead to the generation of porosity.

5 Conclusions and Future Implications

This work proposed online porosity defect detection in the SAW process. The feasibility of this approach was assessed based on the real-time classification performance of the hybrid RCNN model. The results showed the model's significant ability to detect pores throughout the welding execution, with a recall score of 76.4% and an inference time < 7.5 ms per millimeter of welding, i.e., less than 10% of the time required to weld 1 mm.

Furthermore, the classification results demonstrated that the variable related to voltage has a close relationship with pore-related defects. As future research to improve the RCNN classification results, the addition of other variables that may relate to the defect under study will be proposed. For example, the welding plate temperature could be a variable that enhances pore detection, given that it reflects the plate's heating state and the possibility of gases being trapped during pore generation. Additionally, another strategy to improve RCNN performance is to use a greater number of welded beads with porosity along their length. This would allow the model to learn from a wider variety of instances with pores, improving its balance between classes and generalization against previously unseen pores. This can be attributed to various tests aimed at expanding the database with instances of porosity, coupled with an increasingly robust model architecture, resulting in an upward trend in performance metrics.

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